

////////////////////////////////////

UNDERSTANDING PERCEIVED CONTROL PRINCIPLES & A FRAMEWORK FOR SERVICE DESIGNERS

Tony Poor / Miso Kim
Carnegie Mellon University
misokim@cmu.edu

ABSTRACT

Desire for control is widely accepted as a driver of human behavior and a major factor in design work, yet despite strong evidence suggesting that the perception of control is crucial to quality service experiences, little has been written for service designers on the subject. We provide a framework to understand how the service experience is impacted by the user's perceived control, supplementing our work with a case analysis of the travel industry and connecting theory and practice with a set of "design lenses" for designers to apply to their own work.

Keywords: service design, perceived control, user experience

INTRODUCTION

Design often concerns itself with the issue of control. Norman (2011), for example, discusses a technologically advanced washing machine that could be almost entirely automatic yet is purposefully designed with a slew of unnecessary manual buttons; the presence of these buttons is superfluous outside of providing the user with a sense of control. Desire for control is widely accepted to drive human behavior in general; DeCharms (1968) theorizes that people struggle to be "origins" (who feel in control of the events in their lives) rather than "pawns" (who feel as if they're at the whims of external forces). The business value of providing a sense of control to the customer in product and service design, then, should be fairly logical; it is aligned with the social goals of human nature.

As design becomes more and more focused on holistic experiences, we believe control will become increasingly paramount. Control is taking on an

absolutely crucial and acknowledged role in many design disciplines; indeed, one of Jakob Nielsen's ten heuristics for user interface design is *user control and freedom* (Nielsen & Mack, 1994).

However, control carries a unique significance in service design. Organizations coming from a product viewpoint might naïvely assume that by paying for a service, the consumer is willingly giving up a sense of control and is simply *receiving* the service in much the same way that he would receive a physical good. A deeper understanding shows this to be a dangerous assumption: since a service is co-produced by the provider and the consumer (Grönroos, 2000), the consumer shares responsibility for production. With this greater role comes a greater need for control; in other words, perceived control affects the customer's productivity in service co-production. Complications arise, however, due to the fact that control must now be shared amongst a wide variety of parties, including the consumers, the employees, and the service organization itself.

Perceived control is a psychological concept that refers to a person's subjective beliefs about his control over a situation (Bandura, 1997). There is evidence to suggest that perceptions may be even more important than control itself; for instance, greater perceived control has been found to be more effective than coping mechanisms themselves at dealing with stressful situations (Pearlin & Schooler, 1978).

This is a crucial idea for service designers to understand, as control beliefs are key to quality service experiences. Edvardsson (1997) argues that a customer's subjective evaluation of his experience forms their perception of service quality, and Grönroos (2000) even suggests that perceived control

is one of the critical factors affecting perceived service quality. Meanwhile, greater employee perceived control is correlated with higher customer satisfaction (Yagil, 2002), higher levels of consumer perceived control can mediate effects of density in a service (Hui, 1991), and there is even speculation that when looking at an experience in retrospect, a person who had a strong sense of control will view it more positively than one who didn't (Fiske & Taylor, 1991). Despite the importance of perceived control suggested by these and other findings, however, little has been done to provide a practical framework aimed at designers.

This paper aims to fill this gap by providing a framework to understand how the service experience is impacted by three types of control beliefs: behavioral (direct control over action), decisional (selection of various choices), and cognitive (intellectual management of experiences). Meanwhile, we suggest sets of “design lenses” as lightweight tools for design teams who hope to apply the conceptual framework of perceived control to their own work. Finally, we illustrate the experience of airport travel through the lens of control; this area is rife with stressful control issues (from a wide variety of viewpoints, including those of the traveler, the employees, and the service providers) that are key to the success of the service.

PRIOR RESEARCH

Perceived control has been extensively researched by psychologists in terms of its effect on stressful situations in healthcare (for instance, a patient undergoing a surgical procedure). Several researchers have attempted to develop a categorization of control types, including Averill (1973), Thompson (1981), Miller (1965), and Lewis (1987).

Averill's typology (1973) breaks control into three components: behavioral (“direct action on the environment”), decisional (the “number of options open to an individual”), and cognitive (“the interpretation of events”). Averill's version of cognitive control is divided into information gain and appraisal, where information gain refers to the information obtained by the individual and appraisal

is defined as the individual's “imposition of meaning” on events.

Thompson (1981) addressed theoretical issues found with Averill's definitions and proposed a breakdown of control into *behavioral*, *cognitive*, *information*, and *retrospective*. Behavioral control, as she identifies it, is the “belief that one has a behavioral response available that can affect the aversiveness of an event” and is quite similar to Averill's definition. Information is considered a control type of its own (rather than being a subset of Averill's cognitive control), and Thompson's concept of cognitive control involves “a cognitive strategy available that can affect the aversiveness of an event” and is separated into two different types of strategies: *avoidant* and *nonavoidant*. Avoidant strategies involve distancing or distracting oneself from the aversive event at hand, while nonavoidant strategies focus on the event by trying to actively control reactions or thinking heavily about the event (for example, imposing meaning on it). Finally, retrospective control refers to “a person's attributions about the cause of an event once it has happened.” Namely, a person may be able to protect their sense of control by retrospectively attributing responsibility over a past event to themselves. This adds a temporal aspect that is not emphasized in any other typologies.

Miller (1965) separated control into *instrumental control* (the ability to make a response that modifies an aversive event), *self-administration* (where the subject delivers the stimulation himself), and *potential control* (where the person believes he has control, but refrains from exercising it). Miller's typology is extremely focused on behavioral control beliefs, however, and is a bit too narrow and focused on administration of health procedures for our purposes.

Finally, Lewis offered a much less well-known typology (1987) that identified the concept of existential control as well: namely, the “imposition of meaning and purpose on an event to decrease its perceived threatening properties.” Existential control notably relates strongly to Thompson's concept of a nonavoidant cognitive strategy.

FRAMEWORK OF PERCEIVED CONTROL

These typologies are often framed by their researchers' own fields and are not necessarily focused on use within the design of services; thus, we have built on their work and would like to advance the foundations of a single framework specifically geared towards practical use in service design. In doing so, we capture many representative qualities of control identified by past researchers while integrating pragmatic perspectives unique to the issues of services. This practically minded framework based on three types of control beliefs: *behavioral*, *cognitive*, and *decisional*, each providing a different perspective on perceived control (Figure 1 below). We discuss this foundational framework in the following sections, and identify how each control type arises from the research of Averill, Thompson, and others.

Figure 1. Our framework of perceived control.

“LENSES” FOR DESIGN PRACTICE

In his renowned book *The Art of Game Design* (2008), Jesse Schell distilled game design principles down into individual “design lenses.” Each lens frames a different principle and includes a concise description and a set of related questions that the designer can ask of their design solution (see Figure 2 for an example). These lenses force the game designer to examine their work from a fresh perspective and allow for easy communication between team members (even non-designers), since design principles are instilled in an easy-to-understand and concise manner.

65

The Lens of The Story Machine

Illustration by Jim Rugg

A good game is a machine that generates stories when people play it. To make sure your story machine is as productive as possible, ask yourself these questions:

- When players have different choices about how to achieve goals, new and different stories can arise. How can I add more of these choices?
- Different conflicts lead to different stories. How can I allow more types of conflict to arise from my game?
- When players can personalize the character and setting, they will care more about story outcomes. How can I let players personalize the story?

Figure 2. A sample lens from Jesse Schell's “The Art of Game Design,” explaining the principle of story generation.

We believe that a similar approach is suitable in our situation, since each type of control belief that we have presented provides a unique perspective that surfaces opportunities for improvement in a service.

The lens is conceptually similar to the more academically recognized idea of a *design frame*; however, we perceive the need for a vocabulary friendly to both designers and non-designers, and feel that the *lens* concept is more conceptually clear and tangible to an audience not familiar with design theory. This, we believe, is crucial, as good service design involves many more stakeholders than just academically trained designers (business leaders, managers, and even employees, to name a few). Thus, as we introduce our framework, we also introduce lenses of our own.

However, our method differs from Schell's in the nature of the questions posed on the lens. Often, the questions on Schell's lenses indicate evident truths rather than tentative, thought-provoking questions. (For example, the phrasing of the example's "How can I allow more types of conflict to arise from my game?" question indicates that a variety of conflicts is universally a good thing in game design.) Due to the exploratory nature of our work and the huge diversity of service problems (which make it very difficult to identify rules that work across all services), we try to avoid such universal truths. For example, "Would it be helpful to provide more opportunities for customers to learn?" is a question we pose on a lens in page 5; note that the question is only intended to raise a perspective that may have been overlooked by the designer, rather than to attempt to provide a universal design principle.

BEHAVIORAL CONTROL

Behavioral control is the sense of control gained when one is able to take action and directly affect an event. For example, imagine a customer on hold with his cable company's phone support; this is a situation notably lacking in behavioral control. The customer can't speed up his wait or talk to anyone; in fact, all he can do is hang up, and even that often isn't a viable option since it would nullify the amount of time he's waited already.

Behavioral control is arguably the form of control that is most well-understood by design practitioners and relates strongly to classic interaction design principles (such as proper feedback, affordances, feedforward, error handling, etc.). Still, there are a number of interesting psychological effects to consider: for instance, even in extremely negative circumstances (like a root canal procedure) the simple presence of perceived behavioral control may improve the experience for the customer. A dentist may tell a patient to make a signal if he experiences too much pain; this gives the patient a sense of behavioral control. Furthermore, there is some speculation that when looking at a stressful event in retrospect, a person who had a strong sense of behavioral control may view it more positively than a person who didn't (Fiske & Taylor, 1991): therefore, the perceived quality of the service experience in

retrospect might actually vary based on the level of behavioral control.

There has recently been a huge trend towards self-service systems with digital interactive touchpoints, such as self-check-out lines in grocery stores and self-check-in kiosks in airports. These are extreme cases of behavioral control since the user drives the majority of the action, and the design of these touchpoints is crucial in reinforcing perceived control.

The Lens of Behavioral Control

A sense of behavioral control is gained when one is able to take action and directly affect an event.

- How can you provide opportunities to allow the consumer to directly impact his experience?
- Is your customer looking for a "spectator" experience, or does he desire more direct involvement in the service?
- Are self-service mechanisms effective, or are there cracks and possible errors that will cause a customer to lose his sense of control?

Figure 3. A lens providing a perspective on behavioral control.

COGNITIVE CONTROL: INFORMATION & APPRAISAL

Our definition of cognitive control borrows heavily from both Averill and Thompson, but uses a variation of Lewis's broader definition: the intellectual management of an experience. Cognitive control is the most complex of the three control beliefs that we introduce here, and, like Averill, we separate it into two distinct components: *information gain* and *appraisal*.

Information gain is the "input" half of cognitive control, referring to the provision of necessary service-related information to the user (for example, well-placed signage at an airport or information about your disease in a medical setting). We henceforth refer to control gained via information as informational control. Informational control is achieved when the consumer is able to access and understand the information that he requires or wants. Knowledge is a crucial element of control: for

example, a self-check-in kiosk at an airport should explain its operation effectively, and useful and well-placed signage should be present to direct people to their gates and destinations. There is experimental evidence to suggest that simply having a sense of informational control can reduce stress; when people are provided with information about a negative event beforehand, their anxieties may be reduced (Fiske & Taylor, 1991).

Providing outlets for learning, too, is sometimes very important. Some hospitals provide libraries where patients and their families can research their illness. Still others may find that the mere presence of internet connections in patient rooms provides an outlet for families to learn about the condition that they're battling; to encourage the use of reliable material, doctors sometimes predict this and provide lists of reliable sites or educational resources of their own. Regardless of the method, the ability to learn about their illness returns a sense of control to the family, who otherwise may see themselves as a helpless entity with all control in the hands of the doctor, nurses, and - most frighteningly of all - the illness itself.

Appraisal, the other half of cognitive control, refers to the personal interpretation of the service experience; appraisal is the way that a person imposes meaning on an experience and includes the availability of mental strategies that he can use to cope with negative experiences. For this reason, appraisal is especially relevant for service industries that by necessity involve a strong element of stress, anxiety, or pain: healthcare, dental care, or even tattoo services, for example.

Like Thompson, we separate these mental strategies into two different types: *avoidant* and *nonavoidant*. Avoidant strategies involve focusing the mind elsewhere: for example, dental services often provide televisions and music to allow the patient to focus attention elsewhere and remove anxiety both before and during treatment. Nonavoidant strategies, on the other hand, are those that focus on the event itself: for example, laser eye surgery is not pleasant, but while sitting in the waiting room, the patient may read a provided brochure outlining

its benefits. In doing so, he is primed to focus on the positives that will come out of the surgery and is able to cope with the negatives more effectively. This relates strongly to Lewis's earlier mentioned concept of existential control: imposing meaning and purpose to an event can be seen as a nonavoidant strategy that can reduce the perceived threatening elements of an experience.

Even services that are not typically thought of as unpleasant may have some adverse factors for certain portions of the population: for example, some people are extremely nervous on boats and planes. Providing opportunities for cognitive control strategies is a potential method of dealing with these issues.

The Lens of Informational Control

Information is a key element of control, and provision of necessary details to the customer helps to instill a sense of confidence.

- Is all the information that the customer wants (wayfinding, instructional material, and so forth) provided to him in an easy-to-understand way?
- Is there any other information that you could make available to increase their confidence?
- If applicable, do you make it easy for customers to learn?
- Is extraneous information distracting from important information?

Figure 4. A lens providing a perspective on informational control.

The Lens of Cognitive Strategies

Cognitive strategies help a person deal with an adverse event. Avoidant strategies focus the mind elsewhere, while nonavoidant strategies focus on the event itself.

- Are there any customers that might feel negative emotions during your service?
- How can you provide opportunities for nonavoidant or avoidant strategies to cope with the necessary adverse parts of the service?

Figure 5. A lens providing a perspective on cognitive strategies.

DECISIONAL CONTROL

Decisional control is achieved when the consumer believes he has the ability to decide in various aspects of the experience: which course of action to take, the timing of the service, whether to participate at all, and so forth. For example, a patient may choose between various treatment options, and a customer looking for support may choose between various means of contact (phone, email, online chat, and so forth).

Zappos.com, for example, recognized one of the most important hurdles to overcome with respect to selling shoes over the internet: most people want to try out shoes before they make a purchase decision. In response, they offer and encourage free shipping both ways; people have been known to order a dozen shoes, try them all on, pick one pair, and send the rest back. In this way, Zappos matches the level of decisional control available at traditional retail stores, while also touting the additional benefit of having a far wider selection of shoes to choose from and the freedom of shopping from home.

However, it is important to note that too many decisions to make and alternatives to choose from can be overwhelming and may even lead to a *loss* of perceived control. A balance must be struck; a user will only have a strong sense of decisional control if their choices are not trivial or overwhelming.

The Lens of Decisional Control

Decisional control involves the availability of choices and alternatives for a customer.

- Would your customers benefit from having additional choices or more control over certain decisions?
- Is your customer base heterogeneous enough to require multiple methods of service?
- Could the sheer number of choices and alternatives you offer overwhelm your customer?

Figure 6. A lens providing a perspective on decisional control.

PERCEIVED CONTROL IN THE AIRPORT SERVICE

In order to illustrate how pervasive control issues impact service quality, we decided to deeply explore one field through the lens of control. We chose the airport travel industry because of its ubiquity of control issues and incredibly troublesome array of design constraints.

We approached 41 students and faculty at Carnegie Mellon University about their experiences with airport travel, asking them to tell us stories about times when they felt like they had no control over their airport experience, times when they felt like they had a great deal of control, and their worst airport experiences period. We've aggregated many of their stories into a rough service journey (see Figure 7), which we use to identify various control issues that illustrate our framework. By analyzing traditional research through a lens of control, our case study provides an example of how new design opportunities and problem areas could be identified via the perspectives discussed within our framework.

AIRPORT CHECK-IN

Airport check-in elicited a few tales of good control from our participants. As mentioned earlier, self-check-in places nearly all control into the hands of travelers, who seemed to enjoy this freedom. Additionally, options at check-in and pre-arrival provided not only the obvious behavioral control, but also an element of decisional control: a couple of our participants extolled the fact that they could choose their seat, for instance.

SECURITY LINE

The security line is practically the spokesman for poor perceived control in services, and was often the first thing that came to our participants' minds when we asked about control. "I feel like cattle in a cell," proclaimed one of our participants; indeed, the words "herd" and "cattle" also came up in three other stories from different participants regarding the security experience.

Figure 7. Some key service touchpoints in a traveler's service journey, illustrating common control issues according to our framework.

The United States Transportation Security Administration (TSA) has given travelers the ability to choose an alternative pat-down to the controversial x-ray scan at security. Nevertheless, travelers perceive this alternative as equally invasive, and it arguably does little to improve the service experience. This highlights an important element of decisional control: that quality of choices matter more than quantity. The added alternative provides no additional sense of control since neither choice is desirable.

Another aspect of the security line is far more ubiquitous in other services: the waiting experience. Waiting touches upon several different elements of our control framework. First, cognitive control is certainly affected: information needs to be provided about the wait time, and providing a sense of purpose to the rigorous security tests can form a cognitive strategy for appraisal. Second, the waiting line often diminishes perceived behavioral control: the traveler can't speed up the process or leave to do anything else without risking his position in line. Interestingly, Disney has experimented with an interesting solution to the latter problem at their amusement parks: visitors can walk up to a line, obtain a "FASTPASS" ticket, then return at a provided time. Each visitor can have one FASTPASS ticket at a time, ensuring a sense of fairness while freeing them up to ride other rides, get food, or do whatever else they would like in the time that they would normally be waiting (Norman, 2011). While we do not argue that this is a full solution for the TSA, whose problems are quite different, we find it fascinating that Disney successfully addresses a similar issue simply by adding an element of behavioral control.

LOCATING GATE & WAITING

Once a traveler actually gets to the gate, flight delays and standby lists often contribute to a poor sense of control. Standby lists offer no certainty to the traveler, and a sense of informational control should be provided by giving travelers a more explicit sense of their chance of making it onto the flight; decisional control can be improved by informing them of their alternatives if they don't.

Flight delays and changes often delay travelers for hours and can destroy entire itineraries. In these cases, cognitive appraisal strategies may help: in the case of emergency repairs, for example, we've observed travelers darkly joke that they'd rather arrive on a repaired but late plane than crash and die on one that's on time. The imposition of meaning on the delay is important: travelers should know that the reason for delay is a good one. Additionally, the information half of cognitive control is important: how long will the delay be? This provides a small sense of behavioral control as well, allowing the traveler to wander off through the airport, eat, do work, or make phone calls without worrying about the plane leaving without them.

Meanwhile, one participant pointed out that she loved when she found out that she was able to switch to earlier flights at the gate. This should be exemplary of great decisional control, but she quickly added that switching involves talking to gate attendants who usually aren't at the gate until the last minute; thus, her decisional control was somewhat stunted.

TAKEOFF, FLIGHT, & LANDING

Many people find the initial takeoff of a plane to be a nerve-wracking ordeal. Cognitive strategies, especially avoidant ones, could potentially be useful in alleviating the stress of flight for more phobic or nervous passengers; however, electronics are generally not allowed at that point and thus they cannot use that avoidant strategy to escape.

Meanwhile, behavioral control and the information aspect of cognitive control are both severely affected during flights. Several of our participants complained about not being able to go to the bathroom for long periods of time, and one stated that she hates not having information about when meals will be or when she will be able to get up and walk around. This points out another potential element of our control framework: namely, that the control “types” are not necessarily mutually exclusive, and indeed often overlap in interesting ways. In this case, information begets behavioral control: being informed about when one will be able to walk around and use the bathroom may make a traveler feel a greater sense of behavioral control.

BAGGAGE CLAIM

Even baggage claim reeks of control issues. One participant we talked to discussed her lack of behavioral control while waiting for her baggage: after being locked up on a plane for hours, she felt like she couldn't even go to the bathroom because she would miss the chance to pick up her luggage on time.

Another participant *did* take a bathroom break and ended up missing the baggage pickup for her flight, but the informational control provided was so poor that she had no idea that she had missed her opportunity or where her luggage was. Her plane was no longer shown on the baggage claim signage, and she waited for nearly two hours, constantly wondered what had happened to her bags: were they stolen or lost? Was she at the right place? A good sense of cognitive control requires provision of important information.

OVERVIEW

Overall, responses validated our choice of the airport as an example of a service with poor perceived control. “Basically, I never feel in control,” one participant stated, while another similarly expressed “whenever I’m on a flight, I feel like I have no control.” Most telling, yet another claimed that “[during] most of the process, I feel at the control of procedures, officials, and outside factors.”

Our brief analysis of the airport experience through the lens of perceived control shows how the framework can be quickly and simply utilized for initial research of a design situation in order to identify overall patterns of control, problematic touchpoints, and opportunities for improvement. Naturally, the lenses we provide can also be used in the actual ideation process to analyze potential solutions from the perspective of control, as well.

CONCLUSIONS & DISCUSSION

Control beliefs form a crucial part of perceived service quality. We have identified a framework that outlines three perspectives of control beliefs (behavioral, cognitive, and decisional) and have also provided “lenses” in the hopes of connecting theory with practice. Although this paper focuses on the implications of our work in service design, we believe this framework is general enough to be useful in a variety of design disciplines.

Nevertheless, this is only a starting point for discussions surrounding control, and many questions remain to be answered. For example, we have explored the effect of control only on the customer or user. Naturally, control must be split amongst other stakeholders as well (including front-facing and backstage employees, for example), and a more holistic view may be valuable. As previously stated, greater employee perceived control correlates with higher customer satisfaction (Yagil, 2002); what other effects are there?

Meanwhile, we have identified that greater control beliefs are often beneficial in a service, but this certainly differs from service to service. How much control is the right amount? A customer getting a haircut chooses to give up most control to someone

with more expertise, while a customer who chooses the self-check-out lane at a supermarket seems to prefer to take on a larger chunk of control.

And while our framework focuses on the concept of control itself, it does not speak for differences between people. Prior research has found that control perceptions vary wildly from person to person: for instance, Rotter's *locus of control* (1954, 1975) represents a continuum between *internals* or *origins* (those who believe that their actions cause events: for example, getting a good grade on a test is because of devoted study and hard work) and *externals* or *pawns* (those who believe that they are not in control of events: getting a good grade on a test was just due to chance or an easy exam). Interestingly, different types of people may respond to situations of low perceived control differently: in a study by Hiroto in 1974, pawns exhibited much poorer performance on tasks with low perceived control than origins did.

Despite these unresolved questions, we believe that service designers can already think about the impact of control beliefs in their work and hope that this framework can be used as a foundation for future design research and practice.

REFERENCES

- Averill, J. (1973). Personal control over aversive stimuli and its relationship to stress. *Psychological Bulletin*, 80(4), 286-303.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-Efficacy: The Exercise of Control*. New York: W.H. Freeman.
- DeCharms, R. (1968). *Personal Causation*. New York: Academic Press.
- Edvardsson, B. (1997). Quality in New Service Development: Key Concepts and a Frame of Reference. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 52, 31-46
- Fiske, S. T., & Taylor, S. E. (1991). *Social Cognition*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Grönroos, C. (2000). *Service Management and Marketing* (2nd ed.). Chichester: Wiley.
- Hiroto, D.S. (1974). Locus of control and learned helplessness. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 70(2), 187-193.
- Hui, M., & Bateson, J. (1991). Perceived control and the effects of crowding and consumer choice on the service experience. *The Journal of Consumer Research*, 18(2), 174-184.
- Lewis, F.M. (1987). The concept of control: A typology and health-related variables. *Advances in Health Education and Promotion*, 2, 277-309.
- Miller, D., & Lieberman, M. (1965). The relationship of affect state and adaptive capacity to reactions to stress. *Journal of Gerontology*, 20(4), 492-497.
- Nielsen, J., & Mack, R. (1994). *Usability Inspection Methods*. New York: Wiley.
- Norman, D. (2011). *Living with Complexity*. Cambridge, MA.: The MIT Press.
- Pearlin, L.I., & Schooler, C. (1978). The structure of coping. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 19, 2-21.
- Rotter, J.B. (1954). *Social learning and clinical psychology*. NY: Prentice-Hall.
- Rotter, J.B. (1975). Some problems and misconceptions related to the construct of internal versus external control of reinforcement. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 43, 56-67.
- Schell, J. (2008). *The Art of Game Design*. Burlington, MA: Elsevier.
- Thompson, S. (1981). Will it Hurt Less If I Can Control It? A Complex Answer to a Simple Question. *Psychological Bulletin*, 90(1), 89-101.
- Yagil, D. (2002). The relationship of customer satisfaction and service workers' Perceived Control. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 13(4), 382-398.